

**TECHNICAL SOLUTION TO IMPROVE THE SUPPLY
EFFICIENCY OF DELINTING MACHINES****Djamolov R.K.
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ABSTRACT

This paper addresses the problem of uneven seed feeding in cotton delinting machines, which leads to unstable technological processes, inconsistent seed layer thickness, and increased mechanical damage. The study analyzes the operating conditions of existing 1LB and OS delinting machines and identifies the key factors affecting delinting efficiency, including seed feed rate, residence time in the working chamber, and fuzziness uniformity. To resolve these issues, a dosing-vibrating feeder is proposed as a replacement for the conventional feeder. The improved design incorporates a dosing drum and a vibrating comb-like trough with a spring mechanism, which ensures uniform and portioned delivery of fuzzy seeds into the working chamber. Implementation of the proposed feeder in the improved 1LB gridless linter is shown to enhance delinting uniformity, reduce excessive seed residence time, prevent seed overheating and kernel damage, and increase overall process productivity. The standard fuzziness level of delinted seeds is maintained at 0.5%.

The efficiency of the delinting process of fuzzy seed cotton largely depends on how the cotton seed is fed into its working zone. In the existing designs of 1LB and UChDM delinting machines, the seed in most cases falls into the working chamber through the feeder under its own weight. In OS machines, the seeds fall directly into the working chamber through a trough. In this case, the flow of seeds being fed is not always stable — sometimes too many seeds fall at once, and in other cases the amount decreases. As a result, the load on the working elements varies and the technological process does not proceed steadily.

OS delinting machines are mainly used for the second stage of delinting and have been operated without feeders, whereby the load was generated as the working chamber filled with seed. Due to the low fuzziness of the seeds, it was permitted to carry out the delinting process in this state, and the increase in mechanical damage was set at up to 3.0%. However, the 1LB gridless linters used in the initial delinting stage could not be operated without a feeder. Because of the physical and mechanical properties of fuzzy seed cotton — the fibers on the surface of the seed interlock with each other — feeders were used to convey them in portions. Nevertheless, the seed mass, while moving in the hopper or feeder, becomes densely

packed in some areas while voids form in others, leading to large portions of seed falling into the working chamber simultaneously. As a result, the thickness of the seed layer in the working chamber is uneven and the operating conditions of the saw cylinder change.

The effective progression of the process in fuzzy seed cotton delinting machines is directly dependent on the condition of the seed layer in the working chamber. As observed in practice, the delinting process begins to proceed efficiently once a certain amount of seed has accumulated in the chamber and the working zone is full. In this state, the seeds move under uniform pressure between the saw cylinder teeth and the working chamber wall, and the fibers on their surface begin to be intensively scraped off.

If the amount of seed fed into the working chamber is insufficient, i.e., if operation begins before the chamber is fully formed, the saw teeth cannot hold the seed in place. As a result, the seeds may be thrown upward by the action of the cylinder teeth. In this case, the contact of the seed with the working elements lasts only a short time and the separation of lint from the seed is not complete.

As the amount of lint on the seed surface decreases during the delinting process, its movement in the working chamber also changes: seed with a high lint content moves in the upper part of the chamber under the influence of the saw cylinder, and as the lint content decreases, the friction characteristics of the seed change and it begins to shift downward along the cylinder. In this way, the seed moves downward through the chamber and exits through the discharge gap.

In practice, reducing the amount of fiber on the seed surface is achieved by partially closing the discharge gap, which increases the residence time of the seeds in the chamber. However, this can lead to the seed overheating due to prolonged exposure of the working elements and, as a consequence, scorching of the kernel, which in turn reduces germination.

Figure 1. *Delinted seeds*

This results in seeds with fuzziness levels ranging from 0.3% to 0.9% being mixed together, which reduces the uniformity of the delinting level.

Therefore, two contradictory requirements arise in the delinting process: on the one hand, the seed must remain in the working chamber long enough for the fiber to be separated; on the other hand, excessive residence time must not cause overheating and damage. In existing designs, this issue is mainly resolved by adjusting the discharge gap, but this method does not always yield optimal results.

Based on this, a need arose to improve the units responsible for feeding fuzzy seed into the working chamber and ensuring its movement within the chamber, in order to increase the operating efficiency of the delinting machine. In particular, optimizing the uniform feeding of

seed into the chamber and its even movement in the working zone is of great importance. This indicated the need to improve the design of the supply section currently in use and the units controlling the movement for forming a roll of seed fiber on a saw drum.

In this regard, it was proposed to use a dosing-vibrating feeder instead of a conventional feeder for the delinting machine (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Schematic of the proposed dosing-vibrating feeder (A) and vibrating element (b). 1 – supply drum; 2 – vibrating comb-like element; 3 – spring.

In the dosing-vibrating feeder, a dosing drum and a vibrating spiked trough are installed at the lower part. The feeder operates as follows: when fuzzy seeds fed from the distributing screw to the delinting machines are dropped onto the dosing drum, the rotation of the drum throws the seeds collected in each vane compartment from a certain height onto the vibrating trough, and the vibration of the trough causes the seeds to spread out and be conveyed into the working chamber.

The varying fuzziness levels among the seeds in the delinted mass can cause difficulties in the subsequent sorting stage: seeds with a higher fuzziness level may not pass through the sorting surface holes and end up in coarse waste, while those with 0% fuzziness may pass through the holes and join the fine waste, resulting in incorrect separation of the seed fraction. For this reason, the standard fuzziness level of delinted seeds has been set at 0.5%.

Therefore, by improving the 1LB gridless linter used in the first stage of the two-stage delinting technology, and by standardizing the fuzziness level of delinted seeds uniformly across the seed surface, the opportunity increases to: improve the uniformity of seed delinting in OS machines at the second stage; reduce excessive seed residence time in the chamber to prevent damage; and increase the overall productivity of the technology (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Improved 1LB gridless linter.

1 – improved feeder; 2 – vibrating comb trough; 3 – spring; 4 – saw cylinder; 5 – working chamber; 6 – blade; 7 – compaction device; 8 – lint outlet channel.

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